

MIRZO ULUGBEK: A GREAT MAN WHO HAS CONTRIBUTED TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE

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Abstract: The article provides information about the life and work, scientific activity and scientific achievements of Mirza Ulugbek, an outstanding scientist of his time, ruler of the Temurid state, as well as his works.

Keywords: «Zij Ulugbek» («Zij i dzhadidi Guragoni»), observatory, astronomy, logic, trigonometric functions.

Mirzo Ulugbek (1394-1449) (full name Muhammad Taragai ibn Shahrukh ibn Temur Ulugbek Guragan) [1:5] was a great Uzbek astronomer, mathematician and statesman, grandson of Amir Temur, occupying an important place in the historical arena. He is known for his contribution to science, culture, as well as for building the greatest astronomical observatory of his time. The life and activity of Mirza Ulugbek is one of the important pages of scientific progress in the history of the Uzbek nation. Mirza Ulugbek was born on 22 March 1394 in Samarkand. Being the son of Shahrukh son of Amir Temur, he was characterised from early childhood by his interest in science. During his youth he studied Arabic, Persian and Turkic languages, and in particular gained a profound knowledge of mathematics and astronomy. Ulugbek greatly valued education and endeavoured to create a scientific environment by gathering the best scholars of his time. Mirza Ulugbek's greatest achievement is the Ulugbek Observatory, built in the 1420s in the city of Samarkand. This observatory was once equipped with the most modern astronomical equipment and as a result of the research conducted there, valuable information about the exact positions of the stars was collected. Ulugbek created an astronomical table called «Zij Ulugbek». This table contains the exact coordinates of 1018 stars. His work served as a foundation for astronomers and scientists of the next generation.

Ulugbek's research on stars is recognised as an important part of his scientific legacy. Mirza Ulugbek paid great attention not only to astronomy but also to mathematics. He made a great contribution to the development of trigonometric functions and practices. In his scientific activity Ulugbek strove to solve the most difficult mathematical problems of his time and wrote many scientific works.

In his time, he patronised many literary figures, musicians and artists. The madrasas established in Samarkand served to continue Ulugbek's scientific and cultural legacy.

Mirza Ulugbek's scientific activity and his contribution to culture are closely related to the environment that developed during his life. Samarkand, with its rich history and culture, was the centre of science and art at that time. Through his scientific research, Ulugbek played a major role not only in the field of astronomy and mathematics of his time, but also in the development of oriental science in general [1:4].

Ulugbek observatory is an integral part of his scientific heritage, the research conducted here brought revolutionary achievements not only in determining the positions of stars but also in the field of astronomical observations. The observatory was once equipped with the most modern instruments, with the help of which astronomers were able to accurately follow the movement of stars and their positions. Ulugbek work *Zij Ulugbek*, including the results of these studies, served as an important source for the next generation of astronomers.

Ulugbek's contribution to mathematics is also very important. He made great strides in the study of trigonometric functions and their practical applications. His mathematical works, such as the continuation of Al-Khwarizmi's works, led to further development of mathematical formulae and theorems. Ulugbek's mathematical works served as a basis not only for astronomy but also for other sciences [1:1].

Along with Ulugbek's scientific activities, his interest in culture and art deserves special attention. He established many madrasas and scientific institutions in Samarkand and made a great contribution to the development of science and culture. These madrasas taught not only astronomy and mathematics, but also literature, history and philosophy. Many famous poets and writers grew up under Ulugbek's patronage. Through their works one can see the richness and diversity of the culture of that time.

Throughout his reign, Ulugbek faced many difficulties. The political struggles and internal conflicts that arose during the last years of Amir Temur's

reign had a negative impact on his scholarly work [1:2]. However, despite these difficulties, Ulugbek strived to achieve his goals and continued to contribute to science.

Ulugbek scientific legacy remained significant not only in his time, but also for generations to come. His works were studied by European scientists and recognised as achievements of Eastern astronomy. Ulugbek astronomical tables and trigonometric works laid the foundation for the emergence of new scientific concepts in Europe.

As a result of continued research, Ulugbek legacy is still being studied today. Modern astronomers and mathematicians, analysing his works, discover new knowledge. By studying Ulugbek works, one can understand not only the achievements in the field of science, but also the development of culture and art of that time.

In the modern period, there are many events dedicated to the life and work of Mirza Ulugbek. Located in Samarkand, the Ulugbek Observatory is now one of the important tourist attractions [1:3]. Various events, seminars and conferences are held here every year where information about Ulugbek scientific heritage is presented.

Thus, Mirza Ulugbek is known not only as one of the great scientists of his time, but also as a person who left a great mark in science, culture and art. His achievements and works have not lost their significance even today and serve as a source of inspiration for scientists of the new generation. Ulugbek scientific legacy will continue to strengthen his place in the history of mankind, inspire and transmit knowledge to future generations. Mirza Ulugbek occupies a special place in history with his scientific achievements, cultural contributions and development of the brightest ideas of his time. His works are an important basis for the development of Uzbek science and have not lost their significance today. Mirza Ulugbek legacy is recognised not only in Uzbek science but also throughout the world. As a true scientist and personality, he has shown us the power of science and its importance in the life of humankind.

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